
Effect of Employee Engagement Dimensions on Performance in Broadcast Media Organizations in Lagos, Nigeria

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Abstract

A multidimensional approach to employee engagement in broadcast media organizations deserves more attention due to its role as a key facilitator of enhanced performance. This study examined the effect of employee engagement dimensions on performance in selected broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria. Specifically, the study evaluated the effects of cognitive, affective and behavioural dimensions of employee engagement on performance in selected broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria. Purposive sampling method was used to select three hundred and thirty-eight (338) employees of Lagos Television, Television Continental, Lagos, Radio Lagos and Max FM Lagos, as respondents for the study. Data was gathered with the aid of structured questionnaire, while Multivariate Regression Analysis (MRA) was used for data analysis. Findings revealed that cognitive dimension of employee engagement has P-value of 0.000, affective dimension of employee engagement has P-value of 0.040 and behavioural dimension of employee engagement has P-value of 0.020. This implies that the dimensions of employee engagement exerted significant positive effect on performance in the selected broadcast media organisations. The study concluded that employee engagement dimensions have significant positive effect on performance in the selected broadcast media organizations. It was recommended that the organisations should pay greater attention to how the employee engagement dimensions can be harnessed for improved performance of their workforce.

Keywords: Employee Engagement Dimensions, cognitive Dimension, affective Dimension, behavioural dimension, Employee Performance, Broadcast Media Organizations, Lagos, Nigeria.

1.0 Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving business landscape, organizations are increasingly recognizing the pivotal role that employee engagement plays in driving sustainable success and achieving competitive advantage (Sakthimala and Deepalakshmi, 2023). Rao, Narayana, and Niranjana (2021) asserted that employee engagement is a powerful tool that can assist organizations in transforming their employees from strategic tools to strategic partners. Hence, organizations must go beyond employee motivational strategies and incorporate workplace practices that promote employee engagement (Beri and Gulati, 2021).

According to Balogun and Afolabi (2018), organizations globally have become much more aware of the importance of their human resources serving as a competitive edge over their competitors; through their performance, employees create a competitive edge for their organizations. Therefore, organizations should find ways to embed engagement strategies into the overall organization's policies to achieve the highest possible levels of performance from their employees. Albrecht *et al.*, (2015) concluded that human resource managers need to make it a point to insert employee engagement into their human resource management policies and practices. Also, organizations are required to concentrate on the factors that contribute to enhancing employees' performance because their performances have a direct linkage with the goal attainment of the organization (Biddle and Evenden, 2014 and Nkansah, Gyimah, Sarpong, and Annan, 2023).

Employee engagement refers to the emotional commitment and active involvement of employees towards their work, organization, and its goals. Employee Engagement (EE) is the essential nutrient that modern organizations require in order to thrive (Dixit and Singh, 2020).

Employee Engagement (EE) is a state of employee's motivation resulting into the exerting of his/her full self in the work. Employee engagement on the other hand refers to the condition of being passionate and committed to work and being fully involved, the sense of being empowered to execute the required work willingly by employees (Chandra, 2015). Literature had established positive relationships between employee engagement and organizational outcomes like profitability, efficiency, shareholders returns, customers' satisfaction, productivity, among others. Organizations desiring better work output would leave no stone unturned in enhancing engagement in their employees (Rich, Lepine and Crawford, 2010 and Kokkina, *et al.*, 2018).

According to Kahn (1990), there are three dimensions (also known as components) of employee engagement which are - cognitive, affective (or emotional) and behavioural (or physical) dimensions of employee engagement. Cognitive dimension of employee engagement describes the value that employees share in terms of being recognized in relation to their work. Affective dimension of employee engagement describes the positive feeling that employees have towards their work and its environment; it is the commitment of employees' full emotion to work. Behavioral dimension of employee engagement refers to the commitment of employees' strength, effort and devotion on the job. Cognitive, affective and behavioral dimensions of employee engagement are known in literature to exert positive and significant relationship on organizational performance (Geethalakshmi and Rodriguez, 2018; and Ojokuku, Sajuyigbe and Babajide, 2022). The measures/indices of employee engagement that were used in this study were cognitive, affective and behavioral dimensions (components) of employee engagement. Therefore, if these components are measured in an individual employee, it refers to individual/personal employee engagement while it refers to collective employee engagement when these components are measured in relation to the

organization's employees as a whole (Molestsane, 2017, Kokkina, *et al.*, 2018 and Ukonu, Ikoro and Ukoha, 2023).

Organizational performance refers to the overall effectiveness and success of an organization in achieving its goals and objectives. It includes factors such as productivity, profitability, customer satisfaction, innovation, and employee retention (Robianto *et al.*, 2020). Strong organizational performance is crucial for long-term success and competitive advantage. Organizational performance is the realized accumulated outcome resulting from all organizational inputs. It is the resultant outcome that all the interactions of all factor input translate to. It is measured either economically (financially) or operationally (non-financially) or both depending on the organization under study.

The Operational measurement of performance refers to the measurement of organizational performance by using non-financial indices while economic measurement of performance measures performance by the use of financial indices. The use of operational measurement of performance is found to be more applicable to this study for the purpose of ease of comparison of among the selected broadcast media organizations to be sampled in the study (Ehigie and Jesse, 2018; Sajuyigbe, Ikotun and Obi, 2020; Al-Suraihi, Samikon, Al-Suraihi, and Ibrahim, 2021; and Saad, Abdelwakeel and Labib, 2022). The operational performance indicator used in this study is service delivery (SD). This study examined the effect of employee engagement dimensions on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos State, Nigeria.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The relationship between employee engagement and performance has garnered significant attention from researchers, practitioners, and policymakers alike. Numerous studies have sought to explore the mechanisms through which employee engagement influence various organizational outcome and to identify the factors that contribute to or hinder engagement within the workplace. Despite the growing body of research on this topic, several gaps remain in our understanding of the intricate interplay between employee engagement and performance from a multidimensional perspective of engagement especially in the broadcast media organizations in developing countries. While some studies have provided evidence of a positive correlation between engagement and performance, others have highlighted the need for a more nuanced understanding of the underlying mechanisms and contextual factors that influence this relationship.

Jrucilla (2020) studied the effect of employee engagement on organizational performance of a broadcast media organization in Antigua and Barbuda and found that employee engagement affected their organizational performance significantly. The gap identified in the study is that, the study and several other similar studies examined the relationship between employee engagement and performance of either public or private organization only, however, this study examined the effect of employee engagement on performance of both public and private organizations collectively. This study domesticated the work of Jrucilla 2020 in selected broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria. This therefore requires the introduction of performance indicator that is relevant to both categories of organizations and this led to the introduction of service delivery to the components of employee engagement. In addition, four organizations were sampled instead of one organization that was used in the previous study. Also, instead of using Nvivo Qualitative Data Analysis Software (QDAS) as used by Jrucilla (2020), Multivariate Regression Analysis tool was used so that a more robust outcome can be achieved. This implies that more

organizations and more respondents were studied so that a more robust conclusion can be drawn. It is also observed that there was much focus on the relationship between determinants of employee engagement and performance indicator, this means that the study failed to address the dimensions of employee engagement in its full form, this study examined all the three dimensions (components) of employee engagement which are cognitive, affective and behavioral. The effects of these components of employee engagement on performance of the respondents were studied.

Broadcast media organizations are considered important to the Nigerian society because they are viewed as one of the main channels of information dissemination and orientation of the masses (NCC, 2023) so it is imperative to conduct a study on employee engagement in the broadcast media organizations in Nigeria because a dearth of study seeking relationship between employee engagement (a multidimensional approach) and performance of both private and public broadcast media organizations together was found in the Nigerian context (Park, 2015; Kokkina, *et al.*, 2018 and Geethalakshmi and Rodrigues, 2018).

Research Questions

The following research questions were generated for the study:

- i. What is the effect of cognitive dimension of employee engagement on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of affective dimension of employee engagement on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos State, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the effect of behavioural dimension of employee engagement on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos State, Nigeria?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives for the study were to:

- i. examine the effect of cognitive dimension of employee engagement on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria
- ii. assess the effect of affective dimension of employee engagement on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria
- iii. evaluate the effect of behavioural dimension of employee engagement on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria

Hypotheses of the Study

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study:

H₀₁: Cognitive dimension of employee engagement has no significant effect on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria

H₀₂: Affective dimension of employee engagement has no significant effect on performance in selected broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria.

H₀₃: Behavioral dimension of employee engagement has no significant effect on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Engagement

Employee engagement was defined as the full attachment of employees' whole self to work roles. It was considered a goal-oriented psychological state in which an employee completely concentrated on the activity at hand. It also describes the degree to which workers are content

with their work, feel valued by their employer, and demonstrate a positive attitude and dedication to their organization in order to secure future organizational success (Shuck and Wollard, 2010, and Diogenes, 2017). Employee engagement as an involvement of employee with work and their enthusiasm for it, is a work-related construct that comprises of cognitive, affective and behavioral components (Nkansah *et al.*, 2023).

Shuck, Osam, Zigarmi, and Nimon, (2017) defined employee engagement as a constructive, vigorous, work-related psychological state which is driven by the preservation, passion, and focus of mental, affective, and behavioral energy. Employee engagement refers to the positive emotional adherence and commitment to a given task role.

Employee engagement is also defined by Schaufeli *et al.*, (2002) as a pleasing, pleasurable, work-related state of mind marked by energy, devotion, and immersion. It is also described as an employee's dedication to their position, management, team, and organization, which encourages effort and perseverance to stay and enhance the success of the organization as a whole. According to Markos and Sridevi (2010), engaged employees are emotionally tied to their organizations and strongly invested in their jobs, demonstrating a strong desire to contribute to their employer's success by going above and beyond the scope of their employment agreement.

Employee engagement itself as a work-related attitude is an asset to an organization because engaged employees rarely nurse the intention to disengage from their employer. It defines the full devotion of employees to their work, resulting in better output in terms of quantity and quality delivered. Thus, Turner (2020) argues that employee engagement is a strategic rather than a tactical or operational concept due to its vast business advantages.

Dimensions of Employee Engagement

There are three dimensions of employee engagement and they are discussed in details below (Bhuwaneshwari and Kumar, 2017).

Cognitive Dimension of Employee Engagement

The cognitive dimension of employee engagement can be defined as the involvement of employees' mentality in the work. It relates to the part of mentality of an individual that embraces logic. It refers to the thinking component of an employee, that is, the way an employee perceives and makes rational judgment about their organization's vision and values and how important he/she is as regards the contributions being made towards achieving goals and objectives of the organization (Molestsane, 2017). Cognitive dimension of employee engagement is a work-related critical thinking (work obsession), and the commitment of the problem-solving skills and innovative ideas of employees to work (Tenney, 2021).

Affective Dimension of Employee Engagement

This describes the state of positive emotional connection of employees to work, colleagues and the organization as a whole. Affectively engaged employees are known for making investment in their job, it also entails a disposition of positive influence on their work. It is the measure of employees' feeling of safety and perception of a threat free work environment. It is believed that role recognition, access to care, regular feedback, empowerment, among others; stimulate positive employees' emotional connection to work (Geethalakshmi and Rodrigues, 2018, Sinclair, 2021 and Tenney, 2021).

Behavioural Dimension of Employee Engagement

Behavioral dimension of employee engagement is defined as an improved mindset of enthusiasm for the work. It defines employees' high level of readiness to take advantage of available opportunity for learning and development for improved performance. Behavioral dimension of employee engagement is employees' commitment of their physical energy to personal growth, professional growth and the willingness to make positive impact at work (Moletsane, *et al.*, 2019). Employees who showed behavioural engagement is such as are deeply consumed and physically available for the job, they are well prepared to turn out highly valued performance to employers (Copeland, 2020). A personnel that is healthy, well equipped, motivated and fully committed to his/her job and the organization is an example of a physically engaged employee.

Performance

Performance relates to the accuracy, cost-effectiveness, thoroughness, and pace with which tasks are completed in comparison to a set of standards (Jabeen and Rahim, 2021). Every organization require talented employees who have the ability to complete their work (Kurniawan *et al.*, 2018), because an organization's success or failure is determined by its employees' performance (Elnagaand Imran, 2013 and Obuobisa-Darko andTsedzah, 2019). Employee performance is defined by Jabeen and Rahim (2021) as an employee's non-financial or financial results that are directly related to an organization's performance and success. Dessler (2016) defines employee performance as the result of the actual performance of an employee compared to their expected performance. Mangkunegara (2009) describes employee performance as work results in relation to the quality and quantity attained by employees in performing their jobs.

The non-financial measure of performance includes: employee turnover rate, employee satisfaction, employee/organizational commitment, service delivery, customer retention rate, overdue assignment ratio, customer support request volume, customer relationship management, customer satisfaction, among several others. The non-financial measure of performance selected to measure organizational performance of the selected broadcast media organizations in this study is service delivery because it is a major determinant of many work outcome metrics (Ehigie and Jesse, 2018 and Jabeen and Rahim (2021).

Service Delivery

Service delivery is an issue of serious concern to business organizations because it tells a lot on the pattern the customer and firm's relationship leads to. Service delivery can be defined as the comparison of perceived expectations as regards to a given service rendered to a given set of achieved performance delivered. It is a comparison of the quality of goods or services discharged by an organization in relation to the expectation of both the producer and the customer. It is also a measure of levels of customer satisfaction of goods produced and services rendered by an organization. It can be considered to be the degree, at which the service provided by an organization falls below expectation or meets expectation or exceed the expectation of customers (Ehigie and Jesse, 2018). Measuring service delivery helps organizations to be abreast of either the concerns or satisfaction of the customers and thereby have a grasp of the service they are rendering. It describes the ability of an organization to retain its customer (Kaur and Bhanage, 2020). Service delivery affects the performance of an organization because it is a determinant of whether customers will quit the organization or not. The dimensions of service delivery found relevant to this study are reliability, tangibility and assurance (Ramya, 2019).

Reliability: This refers to the ability to deliver the quality promised to customers which includes delivery, pricing and problem resolution.

Tangibility: Refers to the conviction developed by customers that an organization is competent which arises from the array of the physical facilities, equipment and technology possessed by a business organization.

Assurance: Can be explained to be courtesy, ability and the knowledge possessed by an organization and its employees which can help them gain the confidence and trust of customers. In a media organization, customers concern about content creation, audio & video quality and wider coverage need be addressed by the assurance index of the organization (Ramya, 2019 and Ehigie and Jesse, 2018).

The Media Profession

According to Deuze, 2007 and Omid, Zotto and Picard, 2020, what typifies the media work in the digital era is a highly increasing complexity and the current liquefaction of boundaries across field, practices, disciplines and categories that usually define what the media work had been.

The term media refers to any form of communication structure created to inform, entertain and educate large audience. It cut across television and radio programming and web material. A media production therefore can be defined as the development of diverse audio and visual devices to deliver message to audiences and also harvest reactions from them (Omid, Zotto and Picard, 2020). The media professionals make use of media contents to get messages across to the larger audience. Examples of media contents are video ads, movies, radio broadcast, music, podcast, among others.

3.0 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Muller, Smith and Lillah (2018) studied the relationship between employee engagement indices on organizational performance (using balance score card approach). The multiple regression analysis revealed that cognitive, affective and behavioral components of employee engagement positively and significantly influence organizational performance. This study was conducted in South Africa and the indices of performance used were customer performance, internal process performance and learning and innovation performance but the study at hand examined the three measures of employee engagement independently in broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria using service delivery as a measure of performance that is peculiar to broadcast media organizations.

In a related development, Rotgans, Schmidt, Rejalingam, YingHao, Canning, Ferenzi, and Low-Beer, (2018) also examined the influence of cognitive component of employee engagement on team-based learning and the correlation analysis revealed that cognitive component of employee engagement is an important predictor of performance.

Gikonyo, (2018), examined the relationship between employee engagement and performance. The result of the correlation analysis showed that behavioural component of employee engagement has a positive and significant relationship with performance.

Amsi, Kiflemariam and Ngui (2022) studied affective component of employee engagement, gender diversity and employee performance in a textile factory in Tanzania. The result from structural equation model revealed that increase or decrease in affective

component of employee engagement results in increase or decrease in employee performance respectively.

Adepoju *et al.*, (2024) examined the impact of employee engagement on performance of the Asset Management Company of Nigeria (AMCON). Based on the result of Multiple Regression analysis, the study concluded that employee engagement impact positively and significantly on organizational performance.

The studies above examined the implications of employee engagement on performance and productivity across organizations other than the broadcast media organizations, however, this study examined the effect of employee engagement on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria.

4.0 METHODOLOGY

This study adopted cross-sectional survey research design, this research design is suitable for studies that involve field enquiries and enable collection of data from a given sample at different location at the same time. Purposive sampling was used for this study. Radio Lagos, Lagos Television, Max FM Lagos and TVC Lagos were chosen for the study because TVC Lagos is one of the foremost private television stations in Lagos that owns highly functional radio station (Max FM Lagos) while Lagos Television and Radio Lagos were selected because they are the only state government-owned (public) broadcast media organizations in the state. These stations are known for delivering exceptional services. Fifty percent of the professional employees of each of the selected broadcast media organizations were sampled, which implies that three hundred and thirty-eight (338) employees were randomly sampled. Primary data is most appropriate for the study because it enables one to gather data from direct sources; therefore, a close ended questionnaire rated on 5-point Likert Scale from strongly agree to strongly disagree was used for the study (Osborne, 2016 and Copeland, 2020). Descriptive and inferential statistical tools were used for data analysis in this study. Multivariate Regression Analysis (MRA) was used to analyze the effect of indices of employee engagement on performance. Multicollinearity, homogeneity and heterogeneity of the dataset were also tested.

3.1 Model Specification

The model adopted to measure the effect of employee engagement (EE) on performance (P) was that of Eliyahu *et al.*, (2018) but was modified to suit this study as follows:

$$Y = f(CG, AF, BH) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

The dependent variable (Y) is Performance (P) which was measured with Service Delivery (SD).

The independent variable is Employee Engagement and was measured with Cognitive (CG), Affective (AF) and Behavioural (BH) dimensions of employee engagement. f represents the function of the notation. The relationship was a parametric regression equation based on the functional effect in equation 1:

$$P = B_0 + B_1CG + B_2AF + B_3BH + \mu \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$\sum P = B_0 + B_1 \sum_{n=1} CG + B_2 \sum_{n=1} AF + B_3 \sum_{n=1} BH + \mu \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Transforming equation (3) to natural logarithm, it changed to:

$$\sum_{n=1} n \text{ Log } P = B_0 + B_1 \sum_{n=1} n \text{ Log } CG + B_2 \sum_{n=1} n \text{ Log } AF + B_3 \sum_{n=1} n \text{ Log } BH + \mu \dots (4)$$

Where:

X –	Employee Engagement (EE) (Independent Variable)
Y -	Performance (P) (Dependent Variable)
CG –	Cognitive Dimension of Employee Engagement (Independent Variable)
AF –	Affective Dimension of Employee Engagement (Independent Variable)
BH -	Behavioral Dimension of Employee Engagement (Independent Variable)
B ₀ –	Constant of the Model
B ₁ -	Coefficient for Cognitive Component of Employee Engagement
B ₂ -	Coefficient for Affective Component of Employee Engagement
B ₃ -	Coefficient for Behavioral Component of Employee Engagement
μ –	Stochastic or Error term

5.0 FINDINGS, DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATION OF RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Table 1 revealed the descriptive statistics of the study showing the minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis. The homogeneity and heterogeneity of the dataset were tested with the mean and standard deviation. When the standard deviation is high, it implies that the dataset is farther away from the mean value which means that the data set showed heterogeneity but if standard deviation of the dataset is low, it suggests that the dataset is close to the mean value and this means that the dataset is homogeneous.

Skewness and Kurtosis were used to test the normal distribution of the dataset. When the value of skewness ranges from -1 to +1 and -2 to +2, it is considered excellent and acceptable respectively but values beyond -2 and +2 are considered as substantial non-normality.

The acceptable value of Kurtosis ranges between -7 and +7 (Menon, 2024). Table 1 showed that the values of standard deviations are closer to their respective mean values and this infers that the data is homogeneous and the fact that values of skewness and kurtosis are within the acceptable range implied that the data is symmetrical.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics of Study Variables

Variables			Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
	Min.	Max.				
Mentality Commitment	1.00	5.00	3.9367	.94656	-.717	.262
Whole-Self Concentration	1.00	5.00	4.2172	.89335	-1.291	1.874
Work Value Motivation	1.00	5.00	4.1584	.84061	-.909	.851
Threat-free Org. Stir	1.00	5.00	4.4389	.71486	-1.478	3.533
Job Security	1.00	5.00	4.1357	.82000	-.805	.514
Career Dev. Confidence	2.00	5.00	4.2896	.73690	-.724	-.103
Physically Present	1.00	5.00	4.3258	.76439	-1.184	2.074
L&D Performance	1.00	5.00	4.4818	.71809	-1.466	2.570
Equipped to Work	1.00	5.00	3.8869	.96806	-.651	-.090
Reliability	1.00	5.00	4.2036	.81975	-.942	1.014
Tangibility	3.00	5.00	4.1041	.70905	-.152	-.996
Assurance	1.00	5.00	3.9412	.93962	-.778	.853
Valid No (288)						

Source: Author`s Computation, 2025

Cronbach Alpha Coefficient

The reliability of the research instrument was calculated with Cronbach Alpha Coefficient. Cronbach Alpha Coefficient of > 0.7 is considered satisfactory meaning that the research instrument is reliable.

Table 2 showed the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient for the research instrument to be 0.925 and 0.875 respectively for employee engagement and performance; this implies that the research instrument used is reliable because the results are above the stipulated 0.7; the results with Cronbach coefficient of 0.8 and 0.9 is considered good and excellent respectively.

Table 2 Cronbach Alpha Test of Reliability

Variables	Cronbach Alpha Coefficient
Employee Engagement	0.925
Performance	0.875

Source: Author`s Computation, 2025

Discussion of Findings

Findings on Table 3 revealed that cognitive (CG) dimension of employee engagement has P-value of 0.000, affective (AF) dimension of employee engagement has P-value of 0.004, and behavioural (BH) dimension of employee engagement has P-value of 0.020. This implies that the three dimensions of employee engagement have positive and significant effect on

performance (service delivery). The result showed that an increase in cognitive, affective and behavioural components of employee engagement will lead to an increase in performance (service delivery).

The R-square of 92% implied that employee engagement (cognitive, affective and behavioural) affects changes in service delivery this much and it is a predictor of performance (service delivery).

The result agreed with Rotgans *et al.*, (2018) and Kuar and Bhanage (2020) that cognitive dimension of employee engagement affect performance positively and significantly; White (2020) and Kuar and Bhanage (2020) that affective dimension of employee engagement positively and significantly affect performance and the result also agreed with Kokkina *et al.*, (2018), Gikonyo (2018), and Gallup (2023) that behavioural dimension of employee engagement affect performance positively and significantly.

Table 3 Effects of Cognitive, Affective and Behavioural Dimensions of Employee Engagement on Performance

Equation	Obs	RMSE	R-sq	F – Value	P
Service Delivery	288	.8727647	0.9152	17.01889	0.000
Exp Vars	Performance (Service Delivery)				
	Coef	Std Err	T	Sig	
Constant	1.52829	.34348	4.45	0.000	
CG	.33649	.06192	5.43	0.000	
AF	.19089	.06595	2.89	0.004	
BH	.04984	.02134	2.34	0.020	

Source: Author`s Computation, 2025

Test of Hypotheses

Findings on Table 3 showed that the dimensions of employee engagement (cognitive, affective and behavioural) have significant effect on performance. Therefore, all the null hypotheses stated above are rejected and the alternate hypotheses, accepted. Employee engagement dimensions have significant effect on performance.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the findings from this study, it can be concluded that employee engagement dimensions have significant positive effects on performance in broadcast media organizations in Lagos, Nigeria. The study recommends that broadcast media organizations should pay greater attention to employee engagement dimensions to motivate their employees towards higher level of engagement to enhance performance.

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